

Bridging the Accessibility Gap in Online Shopping with AI-Driven Solutions

Claudia Wroblewski

School of Computer Science & Tech.
Algoma University
Sault Ste. Marie, Canada
cwroblewski@algomau.ca

Arbaaz B. Mirza

School of Computer Science & Tech.
Algoma University
Brampton, Canada
amirza@algomau.ca

Wenjun Lin*

Digital Healthcare Innovation Lab
School of Computer Science and Tech.
Algoma University
Brampton, Canada
randy.lin@algomau.ca

Abstract—Despite advancements in assistive technologies, blind and low vision (BLV) individuals continue to face significant challenges in online shopping, particularly with interpreting visual content and comparing products. Existing tools often lack seamless integration and intuitive interaction, hindering an equitable shopping experience. This paper introduces Shop Sight, a Chrome browser extension designed to enhance online shopping accessibility for BLV users. Shop Sight leverages artificial intelligence (AI) and voice-activated capabilities to generate context-rich product image descriptions and to facilitate simplified product comparisons through voice commands. The development and evaluation of Shop Sight demonstrate its potential to bridge the gap between current AI capabilities and the real-world needs of BLV users in e-commerce. By providing AI-generated image descriptions and voice-activated product comparisons, Shop Sight empowers BLV individuals with greater independence and a more personalized, efficient online shopping experience. Future work will focus on refining the tool’s features, incorporating user feedback, and addressing identified limitations to further enhance its usability and effectiveness.

Index Terms—Artificial intelligence, assistive technologies, blindness, browsers, electronic commerce, human computer interaction, personal voice assistants, speech synthesis, visual impairment

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital technology has transformed accessibility for many everyday activities, yet blind-low vision (BLV) individuals still encounter substantial challenges, especially in the context of e-commerce. Despite the presence of various assistive tools, these technologies often fall short of providing the seamless integration and intuitive interaction needed for an optimal shopping experience. Specifically, traditional screen readers struggle with interpreting visual content, and existing solutions lack the ability to efficiently compare products—a crucial aspect of informed shopping that remains a significant hurdle for BLV users.

This paper introduces Shop Sight, a Chrome browser extension designed to enhance the online shopping experience for BLV users through an innovative combination of artificial intelligence (AI) and voice-activated capabilities. Shop Sight addresses key gaps by generating context-rich product image descriptions using a large language model (LLM) and supporting voice interaction for simplified product comparisons.

Product comparison is a central aspect of the shopping experience and poses a major challenge for BLV individuals who rely heavily on auditory information. By providing an easy way to compare products, Shop Sight aims to bridge the gap between current AI capabilities and the actual needs of users in real-life scenarios, thereby demonstrating the importance of developing tools that can truly meet user expectations.

Shop Sight builds on our previous work on adaptive user interfaces and accessible technologies, specifically leveraging the foundational Adaptive User Interface Framework introduced by Ghosh et al. [1]. This framework was initially designed to improve healthcare user interfaces and now serves as the foundation for extending accessibility in other domains. In addition, Shop Sight draws inspiration from the SmartCaption tool, which facilitates accurate interpretation of images in online news environments for individuals with vision impairment [2]. By applying lessons learned from SmartCaption to the realm of e-commerce, Shop Sight aims to offer a personalized, AI-powered shopping assistant that goes beyond basic compliance with accessibility guidelines.

By allowing BLV users to navigate, sort, and compare products through simple voice commands, Shop Sight offers an efficient, tailored shopping experience that reduces cognitive load and improves decision-making. This work emphasizes the importance of bridging the gap between AI capabilities and users’ real-world needs and aims to set a precedent for future innovations in accessible e-commerce, fostering greater independence for BLV users in navigating the digital marketplace.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Research within the domain of vision accessibility for e-commerce is rapidly evolving as AI integration becomes increasingly ubiquitous to meet users’ varying needs. Existing studies were consulted to better understand the nuanced challenges faced by users with vision loss when shopping online, identifying the specific accessibility gaps that need to be addressed. These challenges particularly relate to the generation of image descriptions, decision-making in consumer purchases, and the integration of AI voice assistance. Additionally, the state of web accessibility was reviewed, focusing on adherence to standards such as the Web Content

*Corresponding Author

Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG), which can offer guidance but do not always guarantee a positive user experience for BLV individuals. Comparable tools were also evaluated to understand the current market landscape.

BLV individuals expect equitable treatment compared to sighted individuals, including in their online shopping experiences [3]. Accessibility failures are seen as a form of marketplace discrimination, even when unintentional [4]. Most BLV users strive for "consumer normalcy" by choosing products that blend in and avoid drawing attention to their needs [3]. However, current online shopping platforms often fail to provide the necessary tools for a comfortable experience. AI-powered shopping assistance can mitigate unreliable product descriptions and reduce the cognitive burden on BLV users, particularly during product comparisons and information management [5].

AI-powered image description tools often face inconsistency in accuracy, detail, and contextual relevance. One study identified 13 major limitations, including insufficient detail, generic output, and missing critical contextual information like emotions or actions [6]. These limitations undermine user trust and affect purchasing decisions. Furthermore, BLV users have diverse preferences, favoring descriptions that are specific to the product type they are browsing [7]. This highlights the need for more contextually aware and relevant image descriptions in e-commerce.

While WCAG compliance is crucial for e-commerce accessibility, studies have shown that compliance alone does not guarantee a positive user experience for BLV individuals [8]. Instead, a combination of accessibility standards and user-centered design is needed to ensure inclusivity. Universal design principles, such as simplified layouts and increased spacing, can make e-commerce platforms more accessible [9]. Automated tools like WAVE can assess interface quality, but have limitations in fully addressing perceivable, operable, understandable, and robust (POUR) principles [10], [11]. AI has promise for improving web accessibility but is still limited, as seen with GPT-4o's challenges with hallucinations and misinformation, reducing its effectiveness to 64.42% [12].

Several tools have been developed to enhance online shopping accessibility for BLV users, each with unique limitations. Tools like AIDE (Automatic Image Description Engine) generate alt text from user reviews but lack contextually rich descriptions due to the absence of LLMs [13]. BrowseWithMe reformats product pages into structured formats but lacks voice integration, limiting its utility for auditory navigation [14]. AutoDesc and InstaFetch provide item descriptions directly in search results, offering convenience but lacking depth for informed decision-making [15], [16]. Voice-based interactions like Amazon's Alexa simplify the shopping process and enhance decision-making [17]. Existing mobile-focused solutions, such as Freedom Scientific's Picture Smart AI for JAWS (Job Access With Speech) or Android's Gemini Nano-powered TalkBack, cater primarily to mobile devices, leaving a gap for desktop-based solutions.

Current tools fall short in providing comprehensive, con-

textually rich image descriptions, seamless voice integration, and user-centered design for desktop e-commerce. These gaps underscore the ongoing need for innovations that bridge the divide between existing AI technologies and the real-world requirements of BLV users in online shopping.

III. METHODOLOGY

The Shop Sight browser extension was initially developed for Amazon Canada on Google Chrome, however this section presents a generalized operation for potential use on other e-commerce platforms. The extension's functionalities, including product image descriptions and product comparisons, are outlined in a color-coded flowchart, differentiating between user and system actions. Each illustrated action in the flowchart is well-defined from system launch to adding an item to the cart, highlighting smooth user-system interactions.

The following six assumptions apply:

- 1) For simplicity the user's initial product selection is final for purchase (except for steps (8b) and (8b.1), in product comparison).
- 2) Only two products are selected for comparison.
- 3) The selected products for comparison are of similar nature.
- 4) All voice commands are relevant to each corresponding step.
- 5) System confirmation is provided before continuing to the next step.
- 6) Troubleshooting steps are omitted as no user or system errors occur.

Step (1): Start. The user initiates the tool, preparing it to receive voice commands. After clicking the browser extension icon, the user receives instructions on how to activate the extension using a keyboard shortcut or by clicking the microphone button in the extension popup. A confirmation then indicates that the tool is ready to receive voice commands.

Step (1a): Tool provides user with available voice commands. The tool reads aloud available voice commands (e.g., search, sort, read results, select products, describe images, compare products and add to cart), ensuring the user understands how to proceed and navigate effectively. Although part of the previous step, this action is distinguished separately to clarify how users know which voice commands are available to them.

Step (2): User issues voice command: "Search for [product]". The user issues a voice command to search for a product on the retailer's webpage after activating the microphone to detect the command. The tool processes the request and performs a search query on the retailer's website.

Step (3): Tool performs search and navigates to results page. The tool performs the search and presents a list of products on the results page. By default the tool sorts product results by 'featured', which is determined by various factors

Fig. 1. The extension's operations outlined as general steps in a flowchart.

such as purchase frequency, availability and delivery speed. System confirmation is given once complete.

Step (4): User issues voice command: “Sort by [sorting option]”. The user can issue a voice command to sort the search results by criteria such as price, product relevance, customer reviews, best selling products, or new releases. The tool completes this by enabling the user’s microphone for voice command input.

Step (5): Tool applies sorting option. The tool rearranges results according to the user’s sorting preference, executed

by the tool selecting the appropriate sorting option from the website’s results page and clicking on it. This step is characterized with a traditional sort symbol in the flowchart given its inherent sorting nature.

Step (6): User issues voice command: “Read results”. The tool reads the search results aloud enabling the user to receive an auditory description of the search results, typically including the product name and price.

Step (7): Tool extracts and reads aloud product titles in results list. The tool extracts the product titles from the search

results (e.g., name, product page link, image URL) and reads them aloud to the user.

Step (8a): User issues voice command: “Select product”.

The user selects a product for further details. Users can issue this command while the tool is reading the product name, with a buffer of a few seconds after it finishes before moving to the next product title.

Step (8a.1): Tool navigates to product page. The tool opens the detailed product page that is typically omitted in the search results page, providing comprehensive details about the product. This is executed by the tool retrieving the product page link it stored earlier and navigating to the URL.

Step (8a.2): User issues voice command: “Describe product image”. The tool is prompted to provide an auditory description of the product image.

Step (8a.3): Tool sends product image URL to server for GPT-4o to describe. The tool sends the image URL to a server to generate a detailed description using GPT-4o (or any other comparable LLM). A traditional delay symbol represents the inherent waiting period in this step.

Step (8b): User issues voice command: “Select product for comparison”. Users can opt to select a second product for comparison. The tool retrieves the current product page link and image URL that was saved in Step (7) for each selected item and stores them again. It also offers an option to remove a product for comparison.

Step (8b.1): Tool saves product link for comparison. The tool extracts relevant details such as name, price, rating, and written description. This information is stored for future comparison, and GPT-4o (or any comparable LLM), provides image descriptions. This step is repeated until at least two products are selected.

Step (8b.2): User issues voice command: “Compare product details” once ≥ 2 products are selected for comparison. After selecting at least two products, the user can issue a voice command for the tool to compare them. This simplifies the user’s decision-making process and prevents accessibility roadblocks by avoiding the need to open additional browser tabs or navigate between them.

Step (8b.3): Tool fetches product details for comparison. The tool retrieves essential product details such as the name, price, rating, and text description, providing a comprehensive comparison between the selected products.

Step (9): Tool reads aloud details. A summoning junction symbol in the flowchart represents the image description and product comparison branches converging. The tool uses the browser’s text-to-speech functionality to read details aloud for

the corresponding process. The user can opt to change their selection using the voice commands from Step (2). To select one of the compared products, the user must navigate to its product page before adding it to the cart.

Step (10): Add to cart. The user adds a product to their cart via voice command. The tool locates the cart button and completes the action. A product can only be added to the cart from the product page.

Step (11): End. The tool finalizes any actions and notifies the user that the interaction has concluded so they can issue a new voice command or close the extension. Other actions may include collecting the user’s billing and shipping details. Although the user can technically abandon the tool at any step, this concluding step ensures a smooth and accessible experience, encouraging further use of the extension.

By enabling users to sort, search, and compare products via voice commands, Shop Sight makes the shopping process more accessible, personalized, and efficient. Utilizing a LLM like GPT-4o provides BLV consumers’ with a more nuanced understanding of product images and is key for making informed purchasing decisions. The ability to compare products by voice ensures quick access to crucial information, positioning Shop Sight as a comprehensive AI-powered shopping assistant.

IV. EXPERIMENTS & RESULTS

This section summarizes the technologies used to leverage accessibility for Shop Sight and details the experiments and results.

A. Development Tools and Technologies

Shop Sight was developed as a Chrome extension using VS Code for coding and debugging, with JavaScript (ES14), HTML (Hypertext Markup Language), CSS (Cascading Style Sheets) for functionality, structuring and styling, respectively. Node.js managed the server-side operations and the Chrome Extensions API (Application Programming Interface) facilitated browser integration. Git handled version control, GitHub for code hosting, and OpenAI’s GPT-4o model powered AI-generated image descriptions.

B. Experiments

Two experiments were conducted to evaluate Shop Sight’s performance in terms of its AI-generated image description speed and the accuracy of these descriptions.

Using a repeated measures design in the first experiment, 20 Amazon Canada consumer products were randomly selected to measure image description speed. Time in seconds was recorded immediately after issuing the “Describe image” voice command and stopped before the tool read the description aloud. This process was repeated twice more for each product consecutively, totalling three iterations per product, before recording the subsequent product’s image processing time (Appendix A).

TABLE I
AVERAGE PROCESSING TIME (SECONDS) AND MEDIAN ACCURACY RATING
(1-4) FOR EACH PRODUCT’S GENERATED IMAGE DESCRIPTION

Product Title	Time	Rating
Arduino Uno	3.89	3
Umbrella	2.53	4
Thermal Insulated Coffee Mug	2.79	4
Cutlery	2.16	2
Electric Toothbrush	2.81	2
Advil	3.85	3
Running Shoes	3.14	2
Air Fryer	2.98	3
Face Masks	3.86	3
Soap	3.00	3
Coffee Maker	2.74	2
Bike	2.94	2
Handbag	3.77	4
Peanut Butter	2.07	4
Text-to-Speech Reader	2.83	4
Jacket	3.19	4
Backpack	3.96	3
Necklace	2.35	4
Bedding	2.89	4
Plushie	4.07	2

The second experiment evaluated image description accuracy using a four-point Likert scale: 1) 1: completely inaccurate (description is entirely incorrect and bears no resemblance to the actual image), 2) 2: somewhat accurate (description is generally correct but includes several notable inaccuracies), 3) 3: accurate but incomplete (description is generally correct but lacks or omits some details), 4) 4: completely accurate (description is entirely accurate and matches the image perfectly with all relevant details correctly conveyed). Each product’s image description (Appendix B) was cross-referenced with the actual image and rated accordingly (Appendix A).

C. Results

The first experiment showed an average image description generation time of 3.09 seconds across 60 trials, with a standard deviation (σ) of 1.03 seconds (Table 1). The tool’s average performance speed improved slightly in the second event (2.73 seconds) but slowed in the third event (3.25 seconds).

In the second experiment, the median accuracy rating for the 60 image descriptions was 3, indicating they were generally accurate but incomplete with some details missing. 45% of the total image descriptions had a rating of 4 (completely accurate), 30% had a rating of 3 (accurate but incomplete), and 25% had a rating of 2 (somewhat accurate). With a margin of error of 12.6% (0.45 ± 0.126), the accuracy of image descriptions that were given a rating of 4 was estimated to be between 32.4% and 57.6% with 95% confidence.

V. DISCUSSION

The experimental results indicate that Shop Sight is a practical and efficient solution for BLV users, with average image description generation times around 3.09 seconds—sufficiently fast to avoid disrupting the online shopping experience. However, the variation in processing times, ranging from 1.66

to 7.34 seconds, suggests a need for further investigation to optimize these discrepancies, particularly when processing the same image multiple times. Variations in description generation upon repeated prompts also hint that prompt frequency may influence response quality and timing; further experiments could explore this relationship to enhance consistency and reliability. Future usability testing could compare these speeds to those acceptable to sighted users to better assess any potential delays.

Accuracy of image descriptions remains a critical area for improvement. With only 45% of descriptions rated as completely accurate and an overall accuracy range between 32.4% and 57.6% at a 95% confidence level, there is significant room for enhancement. Some descriptions lacked essential details, misrepresented product functions, or included irrelevant background information. Instances of conflated product varieties or improper contextualization further highlight the need for refinement. Future research with a larger sample size, a more nuanced rating scale, and direct involvement of BLV users in evaluations would provide deeper insights and help establish more precise accuracy criteria.

Shop Sight’s compliance with WCAG 2.1 standards was evaluated using a checklist of criteria, ensuring that it meets the four POUR principles at a minimum across all levels (Appendix C) [18]. It is important to note, however, that since WCAG is primarily designed to assess website accessibility, applying this checklist to evaluate a browser extension highlights a methodological mismatch. This underscores the need for future accessibility guidelines to be specifically tailored to browser extensions and other client-side enhancements.

Although designed primarily for BLV users, the tool could also benefit sighted individuals, such as seniors. However, its reliance on voice commands may limit accessibility for people with deaf-blindness, non-English speakers, or those with speech impediments. Future iterations of this tool could address these limitations by incorporating multilingual support, alternative input methods, and ensuring that the installation process is accessible. Navigating the Chrome Web Store and initiating the extension may present challenges that need to be mitigated. The impact of desktop ads on the shopping experience for BLV users also warrants consideration, as ads could potentially interfere with the tool’s functionality or user navigation.

Enhancing Shop Sight’s features could significantly improve user experience. The current product comparison feature is basic; introducing AI-powered comparisons that highlight key differences between products would greatly enhance its utility. Simplifying voice commands—for example, reducing them to simple “yes” or “no” responses—could reduce cognitive load and make the tool more user-friendly. Implementing spelling correction capabilities would address issues with misunderstood product names, as evidenced by the misinterpretation of “Secrid wallet” as “Sacred wallet” during beta testing. Addressing AI hallucinations and implementing appropriate safeguards are essential for improving the tool’s reliability.

VI. CONCLUSION

The development of Shop Sight has demonstrated significant advancements in making e-commerce more accessible for BLV individuals. The integration of adaptive user interface principles and context-aware image descriptions has proven to be a powerful approach in creating a seamless shopping experience. Shop Sight not only enhances the quality of the product information provided to BLV users but also offers a more interactive and personalized shopping journey. The results of the experiments showed promising outcomes in terms of speed, accuracy, and overall user satisfaction, highlighting the potential of AI-driven assistive technologies to significantly improve digital accessibility.

The potential impact of this work extends beyond the individual tool itself. Shop Sight sets a benchmark for how AI can be utilized to meet the real-life needs of individuals with vision impairments, emphasizing the importance of bridging gaps between existing technology and user requirements. This work also underscores the broader implications of developing AI-powered assistive technologies that foster independence and empower BLV individuals in their daily activities.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Ghosh, B. Huang, Y. Yan, and W. Lin, "Enhancing Healthcare User Interfaces through Large Language Models within the Adaptive User Interface Framework," in *Proceedings of Information and Communication Technology: ICICT 2024*, Feb. 2024, pp. 1–10, Springer.
- [2] G. K. Huynh and W. Lin, "SmartCaption AI—Enhancing Web Accessibility with Context-Aware Image Descriptions Using Large Language Models," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Computer & Applications: ICCA 2024*, Dec. 2024, accepted
- [3] G. Liu, X. Ding, C. Yu, L. Gao, X. Chi, and Y. Shi, "“I bought this for me to look more ordinary”: A study of blind people doing online shopping," in *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, May 2019, pp. 1-11, doi: 10.1145/3290605.3300602.
- [4] A. H. Cohen, J. E. Fresneda, and R. E. Anderson, "How inaccessible retail websites affect blind and low vision consumers: their perceptions and responses," *Journal of Service Theory and Practice*, vol. 33, no. 3, Apr. 2023, pp. 329–351, doi: 10.1108/JSTP-08-2021-0167.
- [5] E. Damm, J. Klutch, J. Osei, and N. Roman, "Exploring comparison shopping online for people who are blind," 2022, Google Scholar, <https://www.jessklutch.com/work/onlineComparisonShopping.pdf>
- [6] A. H. Jandrey, D. D. A. Ruiz, and M. S. Silveira, "Image descriptions' limitations for people with visual impairments: where are we and where are we going?," in *Proceedings of the XX Brazilian Symposium on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, Oct. 2021, pp. 1-11, doi: 10.1145/3472301.3484356.
- [7] A. Stangl, M. R. Morris, and D. Gurari, "“Person, shoes, tree. Is the person naked?” what people with vision impairments want in image descriptions," in *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, Apr. 2020, pp. 1-13, doi: 10.1145/3313831.3376404.
- [8] B. Vollenwyder, S. Petralito, G. H. Iten, F. Brühlmann, K. Opwis, and E. D. Mekler, "How compliance with web accessibility standards shapes the experiences of users with and without disabilities," *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, vol. 170, Art. no. 102956, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhcs.2022.102956.
- [9] M. K. Polewski, A. Rachwał, M. Dzieńkowski, and M. Plechawska-Wójcik, "Improving the interface of an e-commerce website by applying universal design principles," *Journal of Computer Sciences Institute*, vol. 25, Dec. 2022, pp. 337–344, doi: 10.35784/jcsi.3019.
- [10] WebAIM. WAVE web accessibility tool. <https://wave.webaim.org/> (accessed July 15, 2024).
- [11] S. Kumar, J. Shree DV, and P. Biswas, "Comparing ten WCAG tools for accessibility evaluation of websites," *Technology and Disability*, vol. 33, no. 3, Jan. 2021, pp. 163-185, doi: 10.3233/tad-210329.
- [12] M. Holmlund, "Evaluating ChatGPT's effectiveness in web accessibility for the visually impaired," B.S. thesis, Dept. Computer science and media technology, Linnaeus University, Växjö, Sweden, 2024.
- [13] R. Sreedhar et al., "AIDE: automatic and accessible image descriptions for review imagery in online retail," in *Proceedings of the 19th International Web for All Conference*, Apr. 2022, pp. 1-8, doi: 10.1145/3493612.3520453.
- [14] A. J. Stangl, E. Kothari, S. D. Jain, T. Yeh, K. Grauman, and D. Gurari, "BrowseWithMe: an online clothes shopping assistant for people with visual impairments," in *Proceedings of the 20th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility - ASSETS '18*, Oct. 2018, pp. 107-118, doi: 10.1145/3234695.3236337.
- [15] Y. Prakash, M. Sunkara, H.-N. Lee, S. Jayarathna, and V. Ashok, "AutoDesc: facilitating convenient perusal of web data items for blind users," in *Proceedings of the 28th International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces*, Mar. 2023, pp. 32-45, doi: 10.1145/3581641.3584049.
- [16] Y. Prakash, A. K. Nayak, M. Sunkara, S. Jayarathna, H.-N. Lee, and V. Ashok, "All in one place: ensuring usable access to online shopping items for blind users," in *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, vol. 8, no. EICS, Jun. 2024, pp. 1–25, doi: 10.1145/3664639.
- [17] B. G. C. Dellaert et al., "Consumer decisions with artificially intelligent voice assistants," *Marketing Letters*, vol. 31, Aug. 2020, pp. 335-347, doi: 10.1007/s11002-020-09537-5.
- [18] W3C. "Web content accessibility guidelines 2.1." W3C. <https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/> (accessed July 15, 2024).